

Constituents of *Ficus religiosa* and *Ficus infectoria* and their Biological Activity

K. D. SWAMI and N. P. S. BISHT*

Department of Chemistry, J. V. College, Baraut(Meerut)-250 611

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In continuation to our earlier work on *Ficus infectoria* Roxb.¹ and *F. religiosa* Linn.² (Moraceae), the present communication is related to the study of the constituents from benzene and 95% alcohol extracts of these plants. The benzene extract of the stem bark of both the plants afforded furanocoumarins, bergapten and bergaptol.

The bark of *F. infectoria* and *F. religiosa* after extraction with petroleum ether, was soxhleted successively with benzene and 95% alcohol individually. The benzene extract of both the plants was concentrated at low pressure and chromatographed over silica gel.

Bergapten : Elution with C₆H₆ furnished white needles, m.p. 187–88°; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 224, 252, 270, 308 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 830 (OCH₃), 1 715 (C=O lactone), 1 610, 1 585, 1 130 cm⁻¹ (C–O), which showed it to be furanocoumarin. It was identified as bergapten from its ¹H nmr³, mass⁴ spectral data, m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with authentic sample.

Bergaptol : The C₆H₆-MeOH (5 : 1) eluate yielded colourless crystals, m.p. 279–80°; λ_{\max} 228, 275, 320 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 580 (OH), 1 718 (C=O), 1 638, 1 580 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ 2.80 (phenolic, disappeared in D₂O exchange), 6.16 (1H, d, *J* ~ 10 Hz, H-3), 8.00 (1H, d, *J* ~ 10 Hz, H-4), 6.85 (1H, br, 8-H), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* ~ 2.5 Hz, 3'-H), 7.70 (1H, d, *J* ~ 2.5 Hz, 2'-H). It revealed to be a furanocoumarin which was also supported from its mass spectral data⁵. It was identified with bergaptol from its m.m.p., co-tlc with an authentic sample, its acetyl derivative (m.p. 242–43°) and the methyl ester (m.p. 185–87°) like those derivatives of pure bergaptol.

The alcoholic extract of *F. religiosa* also yielded β -sitosterol-3-D-glucoside and inositol.

Biological activity : In consideration of the antifungal and antibacterial activities of some natural coumarins on *C. lunata* and *A. niger* previously reported by Chakraborty *et al.*⁶, the plant extracts bergapten and bergaptol were examined for their antimicrobial activities. The isolated compounds of *F. infectoria* and *F. religiosa* were assayed against its microorganisms *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. scherichia coli*, *Penicilium gluacum* and *Paramecium* at concentration of 0.2% for aqueous bark extracts and 1 × 10⁻² M for the isolated compounds.

The results indicate an antibacterial activity of both the compounds bergapten and bergaptol against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. An antifungal activity of the compounds against *P. gluacum* was also observed. The aqueous extracts of the plants were found active against *Paramecium*.

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References

1. K. D. SWAMI, G. S. MALIK and N. P. S. BISHT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 141.
2. K. D. SWAMI, G. S. MALIK and N. P. S. BISHT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 288.
3. W. STECK and B. K. BAILEY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 3577; W. STECK and M. MAZUREK, *Lloydia*, 1972, **35**, 418.
4. C. S. BARNES and J. L. OCCOLOWITZ, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1964, **17**, 975.
5. S. TANG, J. C. MCGOWAN, M. SINGH, P. GALATSIS, B. E. ELLIS and R. K. BOYD, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 1995.
6. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. DAS GUPTA and P. K. BOSL, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1957, **17**, 59.